

WILL COVID-19 REVOLUTIONIZE THE HIGHER EDUCATION SYSTEM ?

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Abstract

The nationwide COVID – 19 lockdown has forced schools and Universities to close and send their students home which, in turn, has impacted over 91% of the world's student population. The closure has placed unprecedented challenges on Governments, Institutions, teachers, parents and care givers around the world. In India, 32 crore learners stopped to move schools or colleges and all educational activities brought to an end. Despite of all these challenges, the Higher Institutions (HEIs) have reacted positively and managed to ensure the continuity of teaching – learning, research and service to the society with some tools and techniques during the pandemic. The move to remote learning has been enabled by several online tech stack such as Google Classroom, Blackboard, Zoom and Microsoft Teams, all of which play an important role in this transformation. With the development of ITC in education, online video – based micro – courses, e-books, simulations, models, graphics, animations, quizzes, games and e-notes are making learning more accessible, engaging and contextualized..

Keywords : *Higher Education, Covid – 19 , Impact , Teaching – learning .*

Introduction

The COVID -19 has spread all over the world and forced the human society to maintain social distancing. On 11th February, 2020, the World Health Organisation given the official name of the virus as COVID- 19 where CO stands for Corona, VI for Virus and D for Disease. Formerly, this disease was referred to as ‘ 2019 novel coronavirus’ or ‘2019- n COV’. The COVID – 19 virus is a new virus linked to the same family of viruses as Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome (SARS) and some types of common cold. The first case of COVID – 19 was identified in Wuhan, China on 31st December, 2019. World Trade Organisation declared COVID – 19 as a pandemic on 11th March, 2020.

The first case of the COVID – 19 in India was reported on 30th January, 2020 in the state of Kerala and the person affected had travelled from Wuhan, China. According to the Coronavirus Outbreak in India up to the end of 3rd week of February ,2021 nearly 1 crore 10 lakhs population was affected by the corona virus out of that more than 1.56 lakhs were lost their life.

World Trade Organisation has given some advice to all over world to follow ‘ social Distancing’. So every country started Lockdown for controlling the spreading of virus. In India also from 24th Of March 2020, lockdown started for 13 days. The education sectors including schools, colleges and Universities became closed. All examinations, Entrance tests were postponed. Since the covid- 19 pandemic has disrupted the normal lifestyle of people across the globe, the virtual world has come to the rescue.

At the beginning the schools, colleges and universities were quite confused and not able to understand how to overcome with the situation as the first time this type of crisis sudden compelled to close down the education sector totally. Many

countries are continuing to handle this disruption by deploying different modes of learning through a mix of technologies. In almost all countries, teachers and school administrators are encouraged to continue the communication with learners by delivering virtual live lessons or Massive Open Online Course (MOOC)-styled ones.

Online education, a result of the digital world has bought a lot to the learning table at all levels of education, beginning from preschool up to higher level institutions. The move to remote learning has been enabled by several online tech stack such as Google Classroom, Blackboard, Zoom and Microsoft Teams, all of which play an important role in this transformation. With the development of ITC in education, online video – based micro – course, e-books, simulations, models, graphics, animations, quizzes, games and e-notes are making learning more accessible, engaging and contextualized.

As the digital learning acceleration continues, it also throws light on the digital divide in India. Students from remote districts and those belonging to poor communities lack the infrastructure and the means to reap the benefits of online learning. India is going to witness a 50% increase in students over the next 15 years and although it has many universities and colleges, only few have the facilities to match this surge of students in the future. Online education could be a logical solution to accommodate this problem. The Government of India, for the first time, is allowing Indian universities to offer online degrees which previously were limited to foreign universities. The sudden, forced immersion of learners into virtual learning during this period of Covid – 19 has proved that the education industry is disrupted. Upskilling and motivating teachers, organising counselling sessions for stakeholders such as teachers, parents and students are some of the important measures taken by the administration in the recent past. Making a continuous effort to provide customised teaching – learning material suitable for online classes is another way of facilitating the schooling of children.

The central Government has recently launched the PM e- VIDYA platform, with 12 new DTH channels, one for each class to reach out to all strata's of society. These efforts have proved beneficial to a sizable chunk of the school – going population. In response to significant demand, many online learning platforms are offering free access to their services, including platforms like BYJU's, Tencent classroom, Alibaba's distance learning solution etc.

Objectives

1. To highlight the impact of Covid – 19 on higher education sector.
2. To enlist post Covid – 19 trends of higher education institutes.
3. To find out challenges in the field of higher education.

Methodology:

The research has been conducted by using both Primary as well as Secondary Data. A survey through a structured questionnaire was conducted. The sample size was of 50 respondents to whom questionnaire was sent electronically. The respondent was scattered from different areas which related to higher education field. The sample size consists of population between the age of 25 to 65 years. The secondary data was collected from suitable sources like different research papers, Journals, websites etc.

Higher Education Post – Covid – 19 :

The opportunities created by the pandemic Covid – 19 will lead towards a better tomorrow. New day brings new

technologies to face the new challenges and to solve the problems of mode of learning. There are some challenges for online teaching – learning:

- 1. Enhancing teachers digital skills :** Distance education has been primarily based on the use of digital technologies such as email, online courses and document – sharing platforms, the crises has highlighted the need to develop teachers' technical literacy. Many teachers still lack the required knowledge, skills and tools to design quality online learning material. It is also necessary for teachers to embrace the various features offered by digital tools, such as audio, video, text, live sessions and interactive games, they also need to be trained in the basic principles of how to effectively use these tools for students engagement and learning.
- 2. Lack of Support Facilities :** Many families have experienced challenges in accessing technologies, and numerous parents have experienced difficulties in terms of their abilities and availability to support their children in their learning and in the use of technologies. Despite students acceptance of technological tools in their lives, the reality of the situation depicts a different scenario altogether. Findings reveal that majority of the learners do not have access to mobile gadgets not even smart phones.
- 3. Infrastructure Support :** In India even the most high performing institutions may not be that well equipped to offer online learning for all students at such a large scale. It must be established that to deliver effective both, the online and blended learning there needs to be appropriate ITC support in way of infrastructure and tools as well as hardware and software support system. There is no doubt that the integration of the ITC as an instructional device in academic courses has escalated at a rapid rate.

Subsequently, universities and colleges have started implementing applications.

Data Collection & Analysis :

1. 50 responses collected through the Google Form.

Gender	Male	Female	Total
No. Of Responses	22	28	50
Percentage	44%	56%	100

Interpretations : From the above findings 44% of the respondent are male population and 56 % are female.

2. Age group of the respondent :

Age Group	25- 35	35- 45	45- 55	55 -65	Total
No. of Responses	15	22	11	2	50
Percentage	30%	44%	22%	4%	100

Interpretations : From the respondent 74% of the population are below 45 years age.

3. Location of the Institution

Location	Urban	Semi – Urban	Rural	Total
No. of Responses	41	7	2	50
Percentage	82 %	14%	4%	100

Interpretations : Out of the respondent most of them are working in the Urban areas.

4. Were you using online mode of teaching before Covid -19.

Interpretations: Out of the respondent only 22% were teaching online mode previously, remaining were not using online mode of teaching earlier.

5. Has Covid - 19 given a new dimension to teaching - learning Process.

Interpretations : The study shows that 98% of the respondents agreed that the Covid– 19 given the new dimension to teaching – learning process.

6. Which of the Video Conferencing you are aware of ?

Interpretations : The study shows that Majority of respondents are aware about the Video Conferencing tools like Zoom, Google Meet, WebEx and Skype.

7. What was your experience in Online teaching in a distance mode .

Interpretations : The study shows that Majority of respondents are aware about the Presentation tools like Prezi, Clearslide, Wideo, Sliderbean, Canva, Google slide, Powtoon and others .

8. What was your experience in Online teaching in a distance mode .

Interpretations: The above study find out that out of 50 respondents 13 are thinking online teaching mode is challenging, 18% are thinking its a creative activity, 18% are enjoying withonline teaching, 20% are thinking that it’s a learning activity even 8% respondent are feelingstressful activity as compared to physical teaching.

9. According to you, which is the most challenging aspect in online teaching for aTEACHER?

Interpretations : The study shows that 48% of the respondents are facing challengingin online teaching as Technical issues, 22% have challenges relating to adaptability, 14% are not able to manage the time, 10% are facing the challenges relating to computer literacy.

10. According to you, which is the most challenging aspect in online teaching for a STUDENT ?

Interpretation: The study shows that according to 34% of the respondents students are facing difficulties relating to technical issues. According to 36% of the respondents students have self motivation problems, 16% students have problem of adaptability and 14% students are not able to access the online learning activity.

11. What would be your objective in using technology in teaching Post Covid – 19

Interpretation: The study shows that 36% of the respondents want to use the online learning as collaborative learning, 28% respondents online technology for blended learning purpose where as 22% respondents for active learning purpose. Few respondents want technology for the purpose of feedback collection.

12. Will Online teaching COMPLETELY replace offline teaching in post Covid -19situation.

Interpretation: According to the majority of the respondents Online teaching completely cannot replace the offline teaching in the post Covid- 19 situation

Conclusion :

This study has outlined various impacts of covid – 19 on higher education in India. The recent pandemic created an opportunity for change in pedagogical approaches and introduction of virtual education in all levels of education. The post Covid- 19 education seems to be an education with widely accepted online / virtual education which may perhaps be a parallel system of education, but not replace the offline system immediately due to many reasons. There are so many platforms are available for providing online education but in future may be more costly. Due to all limitations it's not possible to replace the offline education system

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